

Parity Difference in the Frobenius Coin Problem: - One Odd and Two Even Parameters

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Abstract

The PROMYS 2025 Q6 problem studies the set T of positive integers not representable as $2025x + by + cz$ (with $x, y, z \geq 0$) and asks for the maximum possible difference between the numbers of odd and even elements in T , which is 1012. In this note, we generalize the setting to any odd a and even b, c with $\gcd(a, b, c) = 1$. Through numerical experiments on 29 test cases, we observe that $t_o - t_e$ consistently equals $(a - 1)/2$. We then prove that this holds for all such triples.

1 Introduction

The original PROMYS 2025 Q6 problem considers $a = 2025$, b, c positive integers with $2025 < b < c$ and $\gcd(2025, b, c) = 1$. Let $S = \{ax + by + cz \mid x, y, z \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}\}$ and let T be the set of positive integers not in S . It is known that T is finite. Let t_o and t_e denote the numbers of odd and even integers in T , respectively. The problem asks for the maximum possible value of $|t_o - t_e|$, and the answer is $(2025 - 1)/2 = 1012$.

In this, we extend the investigation. Instead of fixing $a = 2025$, we let a be an arbitrary odd positive integer, and we restrict b and c to be even (while maintaining $\gcd(a, b, c) = 1$). We ask:

What is $t_o - t_e$ for such triples?

2 The Residue Pipe Model

Recall the pipe model introduced in the original solution. Arrange the non-negative integers into a rows (called residue pipes), where row r ($0 \leq r \leq a - 1$) contains all integers congruent to r modulo a , and row 0 is row a for simplicity:

$$P_r = \{r + k \cdot a \mid k = 0, 1, 2, \dots\}.$$

A number is *representable* if it belongs to S , and otherwise, it belongs to T (non-representable). In each pipe, cells corresponding to numbers in T are called *white cells*, and cells corresponding to numbers in S are called *grey cells*.

Existence and Definition of Wall Stones

For each residue r , consider the set of numbers congruent to r modulo a that are representable as $by + cz$ (with $y, z \geq 0$). Because $\gcd(a, b, c) = 1$, the set $\{by + cz \pmod a\}$ covers all residue classes modulo a . Hence, in each pipe P_r , there is at least one representable number of the form $by + cz$. Define the *wall stone* m_r as the smallest such number in P_r :

$$m_r = \min\{n \in P_r \mid n = by + cz \text{ for some } y, z \geq 0\}.$$

Once a wall stone appears, every later cell in the same pipe (adding multiples of a) is automatically representable because adding a corresponds to increasing x by 1 in the representation $ax + by + cz$. Consequently, in pipe P_r , the white cells are exactly those strictly to the left of m_r .

Parity in a Pipe

Let w_r be the number of white cells in pipe P_r , i.e., the number of integers in P_r that are less than m_r . Note that the wall stone itself satisfies

$$m_r = r + w_r \cdot a,$$

because the numbers in P_r are $r, r + a, r + 2a, \dots, r + w_r a, \dots$ and m_r is the $(w_r + 1)$ -st term (counting from 0).

Since a is odd, the parity of numbers in P_r alternates:

- If r is even: even, odd, even, odd, ...
- If r is odd: odd, even, odd, even, ...

Let $\sigma_r = t_{o,r} - t_{e,r}$, where $t_{o,r}$ and $t_{e,r}$ are the counts of odd and even white cells in pipe P_r . Then

$$\sigma_r = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } w_r \text{ is even,} \\ +1, & \text{if } w_r \text{ is odd and } r \text{ is odd,} \\ -1, & \text{if } w_r \text{ is odd and } r \text{ is even.} \end{cases}$$

Summing over all pipes, we have

$$t_o - t_e = \sum_{r=0}^{a-1} \sigma_r.$$

3 Numerical Experiments

3.1 Experimental Design

To explore the value of $t_o - t_e$, we designed experiments covering the following:

- **Values of a :** odd primes (11, 37), odd prime powers (9, 25, 27, 125), odd composites (15, 21). (The case $a = 1$ is trivial: $t_o - t_e = 0$.)
- **Relative sizes of a, b, c :** a smallest, a in the middle, a largest.
- **Ratios of b and c :** close to each other, multiples (e.g., $c = 2b$), extreme ratios (e.g., $b = 8, c = 250$).

- **Common factors:** b and c with $\gcd(b, c) = 2, 4, 6$; a and b sharing odd factors (e.g., $a = 9, b = 6$).
- **Boundary cases:** b or c equal to $2a$, b, c much smaller or much larger than a .

A total of 29 test cases were examined. For each triple, we computed T up to a safe upper bound and counted t_o and t_e .

3.2 Results

Table 1 shows a representative subset of the results. In every case, $t_o - t_e$ was exactly $(a - 1)/2$ and $t_e = 0$. (The complete dataset is available in the accompanying Excel file.)

Table 1: Representative experimental results. All triples satisfy $\gcd(a, b, c) = 1$ with b, c even.

a	b	c	t_o	t_e	$t_o - t_e$	$(a - 1)/2$	Matches
9	6	10	4	0	4	4	Yes
9	12	14	4	0	4	4	Yes
11	12	14	5	0	5	5	Yes
15	6	10	7	0	7	7	Yes
21	8	10	10	0	10	10	Yes
25	6	10	12	0	12	12	Yes
25	8	12	12	0	12	12	Yes
25	26	28	12	0	12	12	Yes
27	8	10	13	0	13	13	Yes
37	38	40	18	0	18	18	Yes
125	6	10	62	0	62	62	Yes
125	8	12	62	0	62	62	Yes
125	126	128	62	0	62	62	Yes

3.3 Typical Pipe Table

Table 2 displays the pipe table for $(a, b, c) = (25, 26, 28)$. Cells marked * are representable (grey); white cells form T . The last column shows σ_r , and the bottom row gives the total.

Table 2: Pipe table for $(25, 26, 28)$. * indicates a representable (grey) cell.

r	$n = 1$	$n = 2$	$n = 3$	$n = 4$	$n = 5$	$n = 6$	$n = 7$	$n = 8$	$n = 9$	σ_r
$r = 1$	1	26*	51*	76*	101*	126*	151*	176*	201*	+1
$r = 2$	2	27	52*	77*	102*	127*	152*	177*	202*	+0
$r = 3$	3	28*	53*	78*	103*	128*	153*	178*	203*	+1
\vdots										
$r = 24$	24	49	74	99	124	149	174	199	224*	+0
$r = 0$	25*	50*	75*	100*	125*	150*	175*	200*	225*	+0
										$\Sigma = 12$

Observe that every odd- r pipe contributes +1, every even- r pipe contributes 0, and the sum is $(25 - 1)/2 = 12$.

4 Observation: A Conjecture

Based on the experimental evidence, we formulate the following conjecture.

Conjecture 1. *Let a be an odd positive integer, and let b and c be even positive integers such that $\gcd(a, b, c) = 1$. Let T be the set of positive integers not representable as $ax + by + cz$ ($x, y, z \geq 0$). Then*

$$t_o - t_e = \frac{a-1}{2},$$

where t_o represents the number of odd elements in T and t_e represents the number of even elements in T .

5 Proof of the Conjecture

We now prove the conjecture using the pipe model.

Lemma 1 (Evenness of Wall Stones). *Assume b and c are even. Then every wall stone m_r is even.*

Proof. Each m_r is by definition of the form $by + cz$ with $y, z \geq 0$. Since b and c are even, any integer combination $by + cz$ is even. Hence m_r is even. (The existence of m_r for each r follows from the discussion in Section 2.) \square

Lemma 2 (Parity of White Cell Count). *If m_r is even, then the number w_r of white cells in pipe P_r satisfies $w_r \equiv r \pmod{2}$.*

Proof. In pipe P_r , the numbers are $r, r + a, r + 2a, \dots$. The wall stone m_r is the first representable number, so it is exactly the $(w_r + 1)$ -st term (counting r as the 0-th term). Thus

$$m_r = r + w_r \cdot a.$$

Reduce this equation modulo 2. Since a is odd, $a \equiv 1 \pmod{2}$. Also m_r is even by the hypothesis, so $m_r \equiv 0 \pmod{2}$. Therefore

$$0 \equiv r + w_r \pmod{2},$$

which is equivalent to $w_r \equiv r \pmod{2}$. \square

Now we compute the total difference $t_o - t_e$.

- For odd r ($r = 1, 3, 5, \dots, a-2$): Lemma 1 tells us m_r is even, and Lemma 2 gives $w_r \equiv r \equiv 1 \pmod{2}$, so w_r is odd. Since r is odd, the pipe starts with an odd number, and an odd number of white cells yields $\sigma_r = +1$.
- For even r ($r = 0, 2, 4, \dots, a-1$): Again m_r is even, and Lemma 2 gives $w_r \equiv r \equiv 0 \pmod{2}$, so w_r is even. Hence $\sigma_r = 0$.

The number of odd residues from 1 to $a-1$ is $(a-1)/2$. Pipe $r = 0$ (even) contributes 0. Therefore

$$t_o - t_e = \sum_{r=0}^{a-1} \sigma_r = \sum_{\substack{r=1 \\ r \text{ odd}}}^{a-1} 1 = \frac{a-1}{2}.$$

This completes the proof of the conjecture. Hence we have established the following theorem. (Note that the case $a = 1$ is trivially included: $(1 - 1)/2 = 0$, and there are no positive integers in T when $a = 1$ because every positive integer is representable as $1 \cdot x$.)

Theorem 1. *Let a be an odd positive integer, and let b and c be even positive integers such that $\gcd(a, b, c) = 1$. Define T as the set of all positive integers that cannot be represented in the form $ax+by+cz$ with $x, y, z \geq 0$. Let t_o and t_e denote the numbers of odd and even elements in T , respectively. Then*

$$t_o - t_e = \frac{a - 1}{2}.$$

6 Discussion and Further Questions

We have shown that when a is odd and b, c are even, the parity difference is fixed at $(a - 1)/2$, independent of the specific values of b and c (as long as they are even and coprime to a together). This matches the maximum possible difference established in the original problem.

Several questions remain open for future investigation:

1. **Necessity of the condition:** Is the converse true? That is, if $|t_o - t_e| = (a - 1)/2$, must b and c both be even? Our experiments suggest that when b or c is odd, the difference is strictly smaller, but a proof is still needed.
2. **Even a :** What happens when a is even? The parity alternation pattern changes, and the maximum possible difference may be different.
3. **More generators:** For $k \geq 4$ generators, can a similar pipe model be used to analyze parity distribution?

7 Conclusion

This note presented a numerical and theoretical study of the parity difference in a generalized Frobenius coin problem. Through experiments on 29 diverse triples (a, b, c) with a odd and b, c even, we observed that $t_o - t_e$ consistently equals $(a - 1)/2$. We then proved this observation using the residue pipe model. Our work provides a complete solution to the generalization of the PROMYS 2025 Q6 problem.

A Complete Experimental Data

The full set of experimental results, including all pipe tables for 29 test cases, is available in the accompanying Excel file: `parity_experiment_complete.xlsx`. Table 3 below lists all cases.

Table 3: Complete summary of all 29 test cases.

a	b	c	t_o	t_e	$t_o - t_e$	$(a - 1)/2$	Matches
9	6	10	4	0	4	4	Yes
9	12	14	4	0	4	4	Yes
9	18	20	4	0	4	4	Yes
11	12	14	5	0	5	5	Yes
15	6	10	7	0	7	7	Yes
21	8	10	10	0	10	10	Yes
25	6	10	12	0	12	12	Yes
25	8	12	12	0	12	12	Yes
25	8	26	12	0	12	12	Yes
25	8	50	12	0	12	12	Yes
25	12	18	12	0	12	12	Yes
25	24	26	12	0	12	12	Yes
25	26	28	12	0	12	12	Yes
25	26	52	12	0	12	12	Yes
25	26	100	12	0	12	12	Yes
25	52	54	12	0	12	12	Yes
27	8	10	13	0	13	13	Yes
37	38	40	18	0	18	18	Yes
125	6	10	62	0	62	62	Yes
125	8	12	62	0	62	62	Yes
125	8	126	62	0	62	62	Yes
125	8	250	62	0	62	62	Yes
125	12	18	62	0	62	62	Yes
125	124	126	62	0	62	62	Yes
125	126	128	62	0	62	62	Yes
125	126	250	62	0	62	62	Yes
125	128	130	62	0	62	62	Yes